

Effects of Body Surface Potential Mapping Lead Layouts in the Analysis of Atrial Signals

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Abstract—Non-invasive identification and localization of arrhythmic driving sources using body surface potential mapping (BSPM) can be an important tool for patient’s therapy planning. This study aims to quantify the impact of atrial tachycardia (AT), flutter (AFL) and fibrillation (AF) characterization by reducing the number of BSPM leads. 19 realistic computer simulations with 567 leads (high resolution – HR) have been used to characterize the arrhythmias with respect to the dominant frequency (DF) and phase singularity point (SP) distributions. Data was reshaped to 2D representations, interpolated to 30 x 65 grids and band-pass filtered ($f_c = 2$ and 20 Hz). DF maps were generated combining Welch periodogram and activation detection with wavelet transform modulus maxima in each lead. Phase was obtained with the Hilbert transform on signals filtered around the highest DF (± 1 Hz); dynamics of SPs were analyzed using histograms (heatmaps, HM) and connecting SPs along time (filaments). The analyses were reproduced for 6 layouts with 16 to 252 leads and results were compared using different similarity measures and analyzing features extracted from the maps. Although a loss in spatial resolution is observed and individual differences might be large, results from the HR setting are translated to all lead layouts without significant differences.

Keywords— atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, atrial tachycardia, body surface potential mapping, non-invasive

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

Supraventricular tachyarrhythmias, including focal atrial tachycardia (AT), atrial flutter (AFL) and atrial fibrillation (AF), are among the most common cardiac arrhythmias in the world and can pose serious risks, such as an increased chance of thromboembolic events [1].

These arrhythmias are driven by localized sources, which can be targeted in radio-frequency ablation therapy to restore sinus rhythm [1]: AT is maintained by ectopic foci. AFL is driven by a macro-reentrant circuit, localized typically, but not obligatorily, around the cavotricuspid isthmus. AF has been shown to be maintained by ectopic, re-entrant circuits and functional rotors, which appear preferably when structural and/or functional atrial remodeling occurs [1].

The detection of these driving mechanisms and their location is crucial to the success of ablation therapies. This is usually done via an electrophysiological study, which relies on catheter mapping and several signal processing

techniques to find the driving source(s) [1]. Non-invasive identification and localization of the driving sources using body surface potential mapping (BSPM) might be an important auxiliary tool in clinical practice before catheter ablation, reducing procedural time and their associated risks [3].

Research based on computer models yields complementary information to that obtained with electrophysiological studies, helping to better understand the excitation patterns both in healthy and arrhythmic hearts, giving a much deeper interpretation of experimental data [4]. However, the conclusions obtained with simulations need to be translated into realistic settings, where a much more limited volume of data is available.

This study aims to quantify the impact on the results of frequency and phase analyses on BSPM from atrial arrhythmias when reducing the large number of leads available in a model to realistic clinical settings.

II. METHODS

The methodology is summarized in the block diagram in Fig. 1. Computer-generated BSPMs representing the arrhythmic mechanisms were processed in time, frequency and phase domains using different numbers of leads, obtaining maps from which specific characteristics were extracted. Analyses were made in Python 3.6.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the project

A. Computer Models and Preprocessing

Computer models were generated as previously described [5]. Briefly, a realistic three-dimensional model of the atrial anatomy was used to generate 19 simulations representing arrhythmias caused by three distinct mechanisms: AT (4 simulations) driven by an ectopic focus; AFL (4 simulations) driven by a macro-reentrant circuit; AF (11 simulations) driven by functional rotors [3]. BSPMs were obtained by solving the forward problem with the boundary element

method (sampling frequency = 500 Hz), resulting in 771 data points, of which 567 were selected by excluding points inside the waist, neck, and arms (high resolution - HR).

Subsets of these points were selected to approximate lead distributions with different numbers of leads: 252 [0], 131 [3], 67 [8], 64 [9], 32 and 16 (Fig. 2). The methods described below were applied for all the lead layouts and for the HR configuration for posterior comparison.

Fig. 2. Lead layouts

Data points were reshaped into a two-dimensional configuration by projecting their positions on a cylinder and unwrapping it. The resulting points were interpolated into a 30 x 65 grid using cubic splines. A 4th order band-pass Butterworth filter was applied between 2 and 20 Hz, covering the spectral components related to the atrial arrhythmic mechanisms [8].

B. Frequency Analysis

The frequencies of the driver mechanisms (f_{drive}) were estimated using a combination of analyses in time and frequency with spatial information from the BSPM [5].

Activation times were detected using a wavelet transform modulus maxima approach [10]. The average activation frequency was estimated as the inverse of the average interval between activation times. The spectral content for each data point was estimated via Welch periodograms (segments of 2.7 s, Hanning window, zero-padded to 2048 points and with 90% overlap; frequency resolution of 0.37 Hz). The dominant frequency (DF) of the spectrum was defined as the peak closest to the average activation frequency, thus reducing the detection of harmonics of the driver frequency.

The f_{drive} was defined as the highest dominant frequency (HDF) along the torso after using a spatial mask ignoring 2% of the highest DF values to avoid harmonics. The distributions of the DFs on the torso maps were analyzed by calculating the BSPM DF range (HDF-lowest DF) and identifying regions on the BSPM where f_{drive} is expressed (i.e. connected portions of the torso with DF values in the range $f_{drive} \pm 0.2$ Hz). The average numbers and sizes of the regions were compared for every arrhythmia mechanism.

C. Phase Analysis

A 4th order Butterworth narrow band-pass filter ± 1 Hz) was applied on the BSPM signals around f_{drive} to stabilize the atrial activity seen on the surface, especially for AF [11]. Signals were downsampled to 128 Hz to decrease computation time and phase was determined using Hilbert's

transform (ratio between the imaginary and real portions of the transform's outcome [6]).

Phase maps were generated for detecting singularity points (SPs), defined as the points around which all the phases converge [10], using a method based on edge detection: endpoints of edges detected by Canny's method were defined as SP candidates [12].

The detection of the SPs is based on the phase progression along 5 rings with varying radii (2 to 10 cm) around the SP candidates. Three criteria must be attended in at least two rings for a SP to be detected: the phase should progress in a range of at least π , the progression should be at least 60% ordered and there should be no phase leaps larger than π [6].

The spatio-temporal distribution of the SPs was analyzed based on filament maps and heatmaps (HM). A filament is defined as the connection of the SPs in phase maps along subsequent time instants, around which at least one full cycle of rotation was sustained. Three-dimensional connected component analysis was applied using a kernel of shape 3x3x64 (6.36 cm x 6.63 cm x 0.5 s) to connect and differentiate the individual filaments, with any two SPs belonging to the same region being assigned to the same filament. HMs are the histogram of the SPs belonging to filaments along time.

The number and duration of filaments were obtained for each model. Clusters of SPs in HMs were segmented with connected component analysis; the number, size, and density (% of SPs in cluster/number of points in the cluster) of each cluster were calculated.

D. Comparison between Layouts

The structural similarity index (SSIM) (1) [13] was calculated between DF maps and HMs obtained with the different layouts to assess the changes in spatial information:

$$SSIM(x,y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2\mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2\sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (1)$$

where x and y are windows, μ represent mean values, σ^2 are the variances and c_1 and c_2 are constants to stabilize the division with the weak denominator.

Sensitivity and precision of SP detection in the different layouts were calculated considering the SPs detected with the HR configuration as the true locations. A window of 5x5 points was used for both analyses (size: 11.0 x 10.6 cm).

Features extracted from the DF maps, filaments and heatmaps were statistically compared between layouts using the Friedman test (post-hoc: Nemenyi test). Significance was $p < 0.05$; the null-hypothesis of the tests is that the measurements made with different layouts are compatible with each other.

III. RESULTS

Figs Fig. 33a and 3b show the SSIM when comparing the DF maps and HMs obtained with the different layouts. In Fig 3a, SSIM mean values decrease as the number of leads is reduced, except for the 32 leads layout, which shows a minor increase in SSIM for both maps in AT and AF. In the DF maps, AF presents the lowest values due to larger DF heterogeneity, in contrast to AT and AFL, where large regions present the same DFs. The similarities in the HMs

are lower than in DF maps, especially for AT and AF. Fig. 4 illustrates the meaning of the SSIM for DF maps (a) and HMs (b). It is possible to see that the overall patterns are maintained in DF maps, although local differences are noticeable. In HM maps, high SSIM may be due to the presence of large regions without SPs, which contributes to higher similarity, even though the position or size of the clusters is different.

TABLE I. sums up the comparisons made between layouts, with the values obtained for each feature in the frequency and phase analyses, as well as the sensitivity and precision in SP detection. When extracting features from DF maps, no significant differences were encountered between the layouts, although large differences can be seen in individual models. Sensitivity and precision were above 0.7 for AFL with as few leads as 32 but decrease more clearly for AT and AF as fewer leads are used. However, when extracting features from the HMs, no significant differences were encountered between the layouts.

Fig. 3. SSIM for DF maps and HMs (mean \pm se)

Fig. 4. Examples of the meaning of the SSIM in DF maps (a) and HMs (b)

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Several studies have been made in the past to determine an optimal BSPM setting, with lead numbers as limited as 8 [14]. A reduced number of leads is of interest for standardization of the BSPM method, the manufacturing of electrode vests and the reduction of the hardware requirements [14]. In this work, analyses in the frequency and phase domains, comprising many of the often used techniques for processing of BSPM atrial signals, were used to assess the loss in spatial resolution with lead layouts ranging from 16 to 252 leads in comparison with a high resolution (567 leads) setting.

BSPM DF map showed high similarity in all lead layouts for AT and AFL, which present more uniform DF distribution along the torso. The similarity is lower in AF, where larger heterogeneity is present, even for larger numbers of leads. This reflects in large differences in the features obtained with individual models, but on average no significant difference is observed.

Similar behavior is observed in the phase domain, where the AT and AFL filaments, more spatio-temporally stable than those from AF, result in very similar HMs, in contrast to those obtained with AF. It is important to highlight that high values in SSIM obtained for HMs may be due to regions without SPs, obscuring large spatial differences in the positions of the clusters. Reducing the number of leads affects intensely the sensitivity and precision in SP detection, reducing the ability of the BSPM to localize SPs in the phase domain. Nevertheless, the resulting filaments and HMs yield similar features in all layouts.

The results suggest that observations made in BSPMs obtained with a limited number of leads must be treated carefully, as spatial localization is reduced and large individual differences might appear in the frequency domain. However, several features extracted from DF maps and HMs are reliable and can be explored even with a very low number of leads.

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TABLE I. FREQUENCY (TOP) AND PHASE (BOTTOM) RESULTS OBTAINED WITH THE DIFFERENT LAYOUTS.

		HR	252 leads	131 leads	67 leads	64 leads	32 leads	16 leads
<i>Frequency analysis</i>								
f_{drive} (Hz)	AT	4.06 ± 0.03	4.06 ± 0.03	4.06 ± 0.03	5.04 ± 0.97	5.04 ± 0.97	4.06 ± 0.03	4.06 ± 0.03
	AFL	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12	4.09 ± 0.12
	AF	5.58 ± 0.23	5.58 ± 0.23	5.58 ± 0.23	5.37 ± 0.30	5.58 ± 0.23	5.56 ± 0.23	5.59 ± 0.22
Range (Hz)	AT	4.70 ± 0.62	5.22 ± 0.71	4.12 ± 2.04	4.30 ± 1.70	3.94 ± 0.75	3.69 ± 1.99	4.61 ± 0.67
	AFL	2.35 ± 0.63	2.84 ± 0.74	3.30 ± 0.70	1.83 ± 0.87	3.30 ± 0.70	3.30 ± 0.70	1.83 ± 0.87
	AF	2.86 ± 0.15	2.85 ± 0.16	2.94 ± 0.23	2.85 ± 0.16	2.83 ± 0.16	2.86 ± 0.17	2.94 ± 0.23
number of f_{drive} regions	AT	1.50 ± 1.00	1.5 ± 1.00	1.50 ± 1.00	2.75 ± 2.06	2.25 ± 0.95	2.50 ± 3.00	1.75 ± 1.50
	AFL	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.25 ± 0.25
	AF	2.64 ± 0.43	2.64 ± 0.41	3.64 ± 0.59	3.73 ± 0.79	3.09 ± 0.53	3.27 ± 0.33	4.45 ± 0.43
size of f_{drive} regions (% torso)	AT	77.96 ± 41.93	78.03 ± 42.04	78.71 ± 41.32	52.37 ± 54.67	53.02 ± 26.76	76.04 ± 46.28	76.85 ± 45.18
	AFL	97.62 ± 2.1	97.62 ± 2.02	97.29 ± 2.34	97.78 ± 1.85	96.81 ± 2.79	97.03 ± 2.62	74.77 ± 24.91
	AF	22.27 ± 10.63	17.07 ± 9.26	10.76 ± 7.60	16.85 ± 9.55	11.21 ± 8.28	5.51 ± 2.34	3.37 ± 1.22
<i>Phase analysis</i>								
Sensitivity in SP detection	AT	-	0.92 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.10	0.43 ± 0.08	0.33 ± 0.08	0.11 ± 0.02
	AFL	-	0.99 ± 0.01	0.85 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.03	0.71 ± 0.07	0.76 ± 0.05	0.16 ± 0.06
	AF	-	0.83 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.03	0.66 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.01
Precision in SP detection	AT	-	0.91 ± 0.03	0.73 ± 0.05	0.53 ± 0.11	0.31 ± 0.07	0.25 ± 0.04	0.12 ± 0.03
	AFL	-	0.95 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.08	0.94 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.07	0.71 ± 0.06	0.14 ± 0.06
	AF	-	0.82 ± 0.02	0.62 ± 0.02	0.50 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.02	0.54 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.01
Filaments/s	AT	1.25 ± 0.29	1.25 ± 0.33	1.25 ± 0.10	1.25 ± 0.18	1.92 ± 0.31	1.44 ± 0.45	1.53 ± 0.27
	AFL	0.96 ± 0.31	0.96 ± 0.31	0.97 ± 0.31	0.96 ± 0.31	1.21 ± 0.45	1.01 ± 0.29	0.98 ± 0.51
	AF	1.16 ± 0.20	1.19 ± 0.19	1.22 ± 0.18	1.12 ± 0.18	1.15 ± 0.17	1.21 ± 0.21	1.62 ± 0.23
Filament Duration (% signal)	AT	78.42 ± 13.8	82.47 ± 14.23	89.93 ± 7.70	88.45 ± 6.43	79.79 ± 9.5	82.14 ± 14.67	69.02 ± 10.14
	AFL	90.98 ± 9.02	90.94 ± 9.06	82.83 ± 9.93	90.45 ± 9.55	88.71 ± 11.29	91.58 ± 8.36	92.18 ± 7.63
	AF	38.4 ± 10.42	38.79 ± 10.39	34.39 ± 8.90	34.06 ± 7.76	36.38 ± 8.59	34.17 ± 8.36	23.75 ± 3.62
Number of HM clusters	AT	4.25 ± 1.03	4.25 ± 1.44	5.75 ± 2.46	5.50 ± 2.53	5.75 ± 0.48	4.5 ± 1.04	5.50 ± 1.66
	AFL	2.00 ± 0.00	2.00 ± 0.00	2.50 ± 0.29	2.50 ± 0.29	3.50 ± 1.19	2.25 ± 0.25	3.00 ± 1.22
	AF	10.64 ± 2.11	10.18 ± 1.83	9.91 ± 1.99	10.09 ± 2.22	12.45 ± 2.63	10.18 ± 2.27	11.73 ± 1.98
HM cluster size (% torso)	AT	0.64 ± 0.14	0.64 ± 0.01	0.63 ± 0.07	0.68 ± 0.13	0.72 ± 0.10	0.60 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.07
	AFL	0.44 ± 0.23	0.47 ± 0.22	0.37 ± 0.16	0.35 ± 0.09	0.34 ± 0.03	0.56 ± 0.33	0.36 ± 0.14
	AF	0.85 ± 0.14	0.94 ± 0.16	1.02 ± 0.15	1.17 ± 0.24	0.82 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.12	0.86 ± 0.13
SP density	AT	2.25 ± 0.48	3.16 ± 1.54	1.93 ± 0.53	2.13 ± 0.55	1.33 ± 0.14	2.49 ± 0.73	2.50 ± 0.79
	AFL	10.79 ± 2.71	9.05 ± 2.49	9.06 ± 2.61	7.42 ± 1.76	7.57 ± 2.52	8.22 ± 2.55	14.76 ± 7.44
	AF	0.62 ± 0.11	0.71 ± 0.15	0.77 ± 0.17	0.80 ± 0.25	0.60 ± 0.11	0.74 ± 0.18	0.63 ± 0.20

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